

THE ASSIGNMENT OF LEXEMES REPRESENTING THE MOVEMENT OF HUMAN BODY PARTS IN ANNOTATED DICTIONARIES IN ENGLISH

Avezova Nigora Safarovna

Senior teacher of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

(E-mail: nigora.avezova.76@mail.ru)

Annotation: Two dictionaries – Webster's and Cambridge annotated dictionaries-were selected as the object of the study to study the assignment of lexemes representing the movement of human body parts in English in annotated dictionaries. The explanation of certain words was analyzed by taking them from both dictionaries, with some words being given examples from only one dictionary. This is due to the fact that a huge difference was felt in the interpretation of some words. An explanation of words whose SEMAS were hardly noticed in distinguishing them was analyzed using the example of an article in a single dictionary.

Supporting concepts- interpretation , dictionaries, catch, grasp,take clutch, hold, lexemes , meaning, observe, explanatinary, expression, analyse, concept, movement.

In the study of the interpretation of words, the expression of the movement of the body organ in the Uzbek linguistic world was taken as a basis. In Uzbek, it was observed that the concept that represented only the movement of the body organ differed in that it was ambiguous in English or represented different movements. Below we will analyze some units.

The Uzbek word for grip (*ushlamoq*) can form equivalence with English words such as catch, grasp, seize, clutch. Even so, these words in English carry information (in the same lexeme) along with the movement, such as its state, what

the movement is performed by means of. Below we observe that this word is given in an explanatory dictionary:

Catch₁

a: to capture or seize especially after pursuit – *catch* a thief

b: to take or entangle in or as if in a snare – *catch* fish in a net

c: DECEIVE

d: to discover unexpectedly: FIND – *caught* in the act

e: to check (oneself) suddenly or momentarily

f: to become suddenly aware of – *caught* me looking at him

Catch₂

a: to take hold of: SEIZE – He *caught* her by the arm as she tripped.

b: to affect suddenly – The announcement *caught* me by surprise.

c: to grasp and hold on to (something in motion) – *catch* a fly ball

d: to avail oneself of: TAKE – *caught* the first opportunity to leave

e: to obtain through effort: GET – *catch* a ride

f: to overtake unexpectedly – usually used in the passive – was *caught* in a storm

g: to get entangled – *catch* a sleeve on a nail

Catch₃

a: to become affected by: such as: CONTRACT – *catch* a cold

b: to respond sympathetically to the point of being imbued with – *catch* the spirit of an occasion

c: to be struck by – He *caught* a bullet in the leg.

d: to be subjected to: RECEIVE – *catch* hell

From the definitions it can be seen that the word **catch** has 3 distinct meanings, each of which has several SEMAS. The meaning of the first word means capture after persecution (fishing, catching a thief). Among the following SEMAS are the unobtrusive, deceiving, unintentionally verifying, suddenly aware meanings expressed, while in the word separated as the second prime meaning, it means to influence suddenly, to take through action, to be beaten, to be exposed.

It is known from this that the word **catch** means related to the movement of the hand. It also expresses various subtleties of meaning depending on the context, the manner of the action, on which object the action is performed. So, in its own sense, this word is understood to mean the movement of the body organ, the touch with the hand, at the same time, the expression of the state of mind.

The grip in the Uzbek language, which will be equivalent to the **catch** words, is explained differently in a two-annotated dictionary:

<p>grasp (C1) to <u>quickly</u> take something in <u>your</u> hand(s) and <u>hold</u> it <u>firmly</u></p>	<p>grasp <i>transitive verb</i> to make the motion of seizing CLUTCH <i>grasping</i> for support <i>transitive verb</i> to take or seize eagerly – <i>grasp</i> the opportunity for advancement to clasp or embrace especially with the fingers or arms – <i>grasped</i> the pen and began writing to lay hold off with the mind : COMPREHEND – failed to <i>grasp</i> the danger of the situation.</p>
---	--

While the Cambridge Dictionary expresses the meaning of taking something quickly by hand(to your) and holding it firmly, The Webster dictionary specifies several meanings of the word: to make an act of possession, to take or pull with passion, to part with finger/hands, or to hug. Therefore, both dictionaries show only a manual action.

The meanings of the word **Seize** (capture) are written to be different in the V2 and S2 lexicons:

B 2: to take something quickly and keep or hold it

C 2: to take using sudden force.

In the V2 lexicon, taking something quickly and holding it (1) or holding it (2); in S2 represents the use of sudden force. From the comments, it turns out that even this word only represents the movement of the human body organ, does not represent various other movements.

The word **clutch** used in the C 2-degree lexicon is given in the annotated dictionary as follows:

Clutch C 2 to take or try to take hold of something tightly, usually in fear, worry, or pain.

As can be seen from the comment, this word is usually used in the sense of trying to hold or hold something tightly with fear, anxiety or pain.

The word **hold**, used in the **A2** lexicon, is thus interpreted:

Hold A2 to take and keep something in your hand or arms.

This word acquires originality with the meaning of taking and holding something by hand.

It seems that the Uzbek word for grip can be expressed in English in several words. This is always done in connection with the context.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary>;
2. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english>
3. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/catch>
4. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/seize>
5. Gafurov. I., Mouminov O., Qambarov N.M. Translation theory // study guide for higher education institutions. - Tashkent: boaston of thought, 2012. – 280 b.;
6. Gofurovi., Mouminovo., QambarovN. Translatanazaria. - Tashkent: boaston of thought, 2012. – B.27.
7. Kholbekov M. Translation and translation criticism // collection of articles. - Tashkent: Navruz, 2015. – 112 b.;
8. Sobirova, Zarnigor. "Чегараланган Лексиканинг Лингвистик Талқини." Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu. uz) 10.10 (2022).

9. Sobirova Zarnigor Rakhimovna. (2022). The Historical Background of the Definition of Barbarism and its Occurrence in The Literary Texts.
10. Sobirova, Z. (2021). Definition Of Barbarism And History Of Occurrence. Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu. uz), 8(8).
11. Sobirova, Z. (2021). English Language Tourism Terms In Vocabulary And Semantical Revision. Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu. uz), 8(8).
12. Собирова, З. Р. Диалектизм Ҳодисаси Ва Унинг Инглиз Тили Шеваларида Қўлланилиши. Scientific Reports Of Bukhara State University, 87.